

MOTIVATIONAL LEVEL AND WORKABLE PERFORMANCE OF SECONDARY TEACHERS IN EASTERN SAMAR, PHILIPPINES

ROY O. ANABO*

Head Teacher I, Dolores National High School, Dolores, Eastern Samar, Philippines.
Graduate School, Eastern Samar State University, Borongan City, Eastern Samar, Philippines.
*Corresponding Author Email: roy.anabo@deped.gov.ph, ORCID ID: 0000-0002-4656-726X

VIRGILIO P. RAPADA JR

Associate Professor V, Graduate School, Eastern Samar State University, Borongan City, Eastern Samar, Philippines.

Abstract

The main objective of this study is to determine the level of motivation and work performance of secondary teachers in Eastern Samar, Philippines. A total of 302 respondents the researcher utilized a survey questionnaire with descriptive correlational research design. To analyze the data, mean scores, percentile rank, frequency count, and Spearman rho correlation coefficient will be used with a 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that the level of motivation of secondary teachers in Eastern Samar is high motivating with a 3.51 mean score. The work performance of secondary teachers in Eastern Samar is very satisfactory with 77.82% or 235 and 22.18% or 67 for outstanding performance. There is a significant relationship between the variables (spearman rho = 0.515; p-value = 0.26). However, to encourage secondary teachers to motivate more in the workplace there is a need to provide financial assistance and harmonious relationships with their co-teachers and school administrators. It is highly recommended to provide necessary technical assistance for the development of the teaching and learning process. School administrators should have quality assurance in terms of teaching strategies to motivate them to learn more in the field of education. Future researchers may conduct a similar study to validate the results of the study.

Keywords: Level of Motivation, Work Performance, Secondary Teachers, Education.

INTRODUCTION

The teacher plays a great role in achieving the educational objectives in the social and economic progress. The teacher's role has not been only transferring knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes but also shaping individuals to fit in the changing world through social, political, economic, and technology.

Teachers who have open personalities, capable of giving, innovation, and renewal, are characterized by having a good education, diversity, sufficient academic preparation, understanding of students' needs and characteristics of their growth, ready to discover their problems and weaknesses. Teachers' motivation can be improved through a sense of achievement and success in performing the task or activity. The teacher's sense of achievement can be increased by encouraging teachers to set specific goals, identify common goals, and set standards for achieving those goals. Identifying the teachers' contribution and performance at work can be done by highlighting the teacher's efforts and contributions in meetings, telling the teacher orally or in writing that his work is appreciated, and allowing teachers to attend

specialized scientific conferences and presenting awards and certificates of appreciation for outstanding work, which all increase teachers' motivation. The importance of teachers being motivated lies in helping them increase their knowledge of themselves and others, and pushing them to act according to different circumstances and situations that make the individual more able to explain the actions of others.

For so many years, teaching has been characterized as a profession that has a physical, emotional, and frustrating impact on teachers (Fisher, 2021). The efforts of teachers are seen in the social and economic development of society, their efforts are not limited to preserving culture but rather by improving cultural heritage in modern life (Lowick and Scanlon, 2021).

In this way, the teacher's behavior can be directed to certain destinations that revolve within the framework of his interest and the interest of society. The importance of improving motivation is not limited to direct behavior but plays an important role in some fields, such as education, industry, and law. For example, in the field of education, it helps to stimulate students' motivation toward fruitful learning (Toste et al., 2020).

However, work performance is an important characteristic of employees in a company or establishment. In an institution, recognizing a person can help them satisfy what they are doing. The public and private schools differ in work performance due to the following: salary, benefits, and some incentives given by the company. Furthermore, Jackson (2018) for them, work performance is an important part of a teaching career and can be increased by building a good relationship with a teacher, colleague, teacher, supervisor, or manager who will guide and help meet their needs and value what they do.

Based on the different studies and experiences of conducting classes and various factors that affect the overall performance of teachers in school. The researcher decided to tackle this issue regarding the level of motivation and work performance of teachers because more teachers today especially the older ones are struggling to cope with different changing mechanisms in teaching such as added workload and also the low salary being received.

Statement of the Problem

The study was able to determine the motivational level of secondary teachers and work performance in the school's division of Eastern Samar, Philippines. Specifically, the study will seek to answer the following questions.

1. What is the level of motivation of teachers in the school's division of Eastern Samar?
2. What is the work performance of teachers in the school's division of Eastern Samar?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of motivation and work performance of secondary teachers in the school's division of Eastern Samar?

Significance of the Study

The purpose of this study is to determine the level of motivation of teachers and work performance. In addition, this will give benefits to the following individuals or groups of people.

Teachers. As the frontline in the educational arena, the result of this study will equip them to handle the emotional challenges of the teaching profession. In addition, administrators will be informed on how they provide needs that will motivate them to work effectively and efficiently in their workplace.

School Head. Being the leader of the school, they will inform them about their teachers' issues and concerns regarding work performance and for them to be motivated towards their work. Hence, they will provide relevant programs and interventions for this matter.

Future Researcher. This study will serve as the basis for providing relevant interventions that would give a solution to the problem.

Conceptual Framework of the Study

The major concept of this study is to determine the level of motivation and work performance of the respondents of secondary teachers within the Schools Division of Eastern Samar.

Figure 1 shows the independent and dependent variables that will be used in conceptualizing the study. The independent variable will be the level of motivation of teachers. On the other hand, the dependent variable of the study will be the respondents' work performance.

Figure 1: Schematic Diagram of the Study.

Definition of Terms

The following terms were defined conceptually and operationally for easy understanding.

Teacher. A permanent professional teacher who teaches students in the classroom setting.

Motivation. It is defined as the capacity to bounce back from adversity and become smarter and stronger.

Work Performance. The performance of the employees towards the organization where they work and integrity possessed by the organization.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The scope of the study will be within the selected schools in Eastern Samar Division. A total of 302 respondents were from secondary schools. A descriptive and correlation design will be used to measure the relationship between the level of motivation and work performance. A simple random sample will be used in selecting the respondents. A little revision of an adopted

research questionnaire will be utilized to measure the level of motivation and work performance of the respondents.

METHODOLOGY

This part presents a detailed description of the research design, research locale, respondents of the study, procedure, instrumentation, measurement of variables, and the statistical treatment of the data that were employed in the conduct of the research.

Research Design

The study will use the descriptive and correlational design of the study. Descriptive research involves the description, recording, analysis, and interpretation of the present nature, composition, or process of phenomena concerning problems with educational results, preferences, practices, and procedures. This study utilized descriptive research it described the data of the level of motivation and work performance. Furthermore, a correlational study aims to find out the direction and extent of the relationship between different determinants of the population under study. However, correlational design is appropriate to use since it describes and determines the relationship between the level of motivation and work performance of the school division of eastern samar.

Research Locale

The study will be conducted with the school division of eastern samar. The researcher randomly selected different schools from both public and private secondary schools.

Respondents of the Study

A total of 302 respondents from both public and private secondary schools were selected randomly from the school's division of eastern samar.

Sampling Procedure

In the selection of sampling procedure, the researcher used Krejcie & Morgan (1970) table to determine the sample size for a given population for easy reference and used cluster sampling technique in the selection of participants in the level of motivation and work performance of secondary teachers within the school's division of eastern samar.

Research Instruments

The researcher utilized the existing questionnaire with two main parts. The first part is to determine the level of motivation of the secondary teacher in eastern samar division. The second part is to find out the work performance of teachers in eastern samar.

To arrive at the exact data to be used in this study, a researcher-modified questionnaire will be utilized. The instrument will be divided into two (2) parts according to the research objectives, as follows: Part I, Teacher Level of Motivation, and Part II, Work Performance.

To ensure the reliability of the said instrument, a reliability test will be conducted by the researchers.

Statistical Treatment Data

The data that will be gathered from the respondents will be tallied, tabulated, and analyzed using Microsoft Excel.

The following variables will be used in the study to facilitate data analysis.

Level of Motivation. This will be categorized and coded as follows:

Code	Mean Score Range	Interpretation
5	4.40 – 5.00	Highly Motivating
4	3.40 – 4.39	Motivating
3	2.60 – 3.39	Neutral
2	1.80 – 2.59	Unmotivating
1	1.00 – 1.79	Highly Unmotivating

Work Performance. This will be interpreted using the performance rating.

Performance Rating	Interpretation
4.500 – 5.000	Outstanding
3.500 – 4.499	Very Satisfactory
2.500 – 3.499	Satisfactory
1.500 – 2.499	Unsatisfactory
below 1.499	Poor

Data Analysis

To determine the level of motivation the researcher utilized mean, percentile rank. In determining the level of work performance utilized frequency count and percentage. The relationship between work performance and level of motivation, the Spearman rho correlation coefficient will be used with 0.05 level of significance in analyzing the data.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher will ask permission from the school head for approval. Each respondent will be allowed to ask questions about the survey questionnaire and to discuss the information and their decision if they wish to participate in the survey or not. Thus, information on the following matters will be communicated to the respondents; how the research will be monitored; the contact details of the researcher; and how privacy and confidentiality will be protected. Finally, the data gathered will be tabulated, computed, analyzed, and interpreted.

Ethical Consideration

The researchers made sure to adhere to different ethical considerations to uphold scientific integrity. Ethical conditions such as informed consent, voluntary participation, confidentiality, the potential of harm, and communication of results were strictly followed. Informed consent will be given by the school heads for approval, and the researchers were encouraged to share the accurate result to be used as basis for crafting programs at school. The participants were also provided with detailed consent letters for them to understand the purpose of the study, how the data gathered would be treated, and how their participation was valuable. The school authorities encouraged research culture. The researcher will make it clear that they might

choose to partake in or out of the study at a time. In designing this research, the researchers considered its needed methodology and instruments to have a bare minimum to no potential harm to a person's social and psychological aspects; making sure that there were no shameful and stigmatizing questions in the survey questionnaire. As much as the researchers wanted to maintain anonymity through data pseudonymization, the design of this study required linking participants' personal information to another variable to generate appropriate and precise results to answer the research questions. To compensate for this unavoidable ethical issue, the researcher pledged to keep the data with utmost confidentiality and would only use the information with the stated purpose of this research.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This part presented the results, analysis, and interpretation of data gathered on the level of motivation and work performance among secondary teachers in the division of Eastern Samar.

Table 1: Level of motivation of secondary teachers

Indicators	Mean score	Rank	Level of Motivation
1. Feeling secure in my job is essential to my continued work and dedication.	3.56	12	Motivating
2. The availability of appropriate educational means increases my motivation towards work.	3.78	9	Motivating
3. I do not come late for my work.	3.05	16	Neutral
4. My teaching experience helps motivate me to work.	3.32	14	Neutral
5. The job description helps me keep working.	3.15	15	Neutral
6. Financial incentives improve my performance at work.	4.34	2	Motivating
7. My work has allowed me to build relationships with my co-workers.	2.92	17	Neutral
8. I volunteer to do extra work to serve the school.	3.80	8	Motivating
9. Good supervision by the school head reduces my motivation towards work.	3.97	5	Motivating
10. I get praise from my school head when I do well.	4.15	3	Motivating
11. Teaching profession frustrates me.	1.77	20	Highly Unmotivating
12. My relationship with my colleagues needs improvement.	3.57	11	Motivating
13. I am happier every time I enter my classroom.	4.05	4	Motivating
14. The school head and supervisor increase my motivation towards teaching.	3.90	6	Motivating
15. Taking pride in my work is an important reward.	3.85	7	Motivating
16. I do not absent from my work.	2.75	18	Unmotivating
17. I feel teaching profession is more fun.	2.55	19	Unmotivating
18. I didn't submit school report on time.	3.50	13	Motivating
19. Salary increase helps me to be motivated to work.	4.50	1	Highly Motivating
20. I feel motivated when no advisory class.	3.65	10	Motivating
Total	3.51		Motivating

Table 1 presents the level of motivation of the secondary teachers in Eastern Samar, the statement “Salary increase helps me to be motivated to work” got the highest mean score of 4.50 with a highly motivating level of motivation. It implies that the secondary teachers in Eastern Samar need a salary increase, give importance to the quality in education, for them to be motivated to teach at school Teaching frustrates me” gets the lowest mean score of 1.77 with a highly unmotivating level of motivation.

The overall mean score is 3.51 interpreted as motivating level of motivation of the secondary teachers in Eastern Samar, Philippines.

Table 2: Level of work performance of teachers

Adjectival rating	Description	Frequency	Percent
4.500 – 5.000	Outstanding	67	22.18
3.500 – 4.499	Very Satisfactory	235	77.82
2.500 – 3.499	Satisfactory	0	0
1.500 – 2.499	Unsatisfactory	0	0
below 1.499	Poor	0	0
Total		302	100

Table 2 shows the level of work performance of teachers in secondary school division of eastern samar, Philippines. Results reveal that 77.82% or 235 respondents acquired a very satisfactory performance rating, while 22.18%, or 67 respondents acquired an outstanding work performance of secondary school teachers in eastern samar, Philippines. Similarly, Baluyos, et.al., (2019) reported a very satisfactory work performance of the teacher respondents.

The results imply that teachers’ level of performance was able to carry their work very satisfactorily in the teaching-learning process. Promote parents and community participation to continue professional development.

Table 3: Level of Motivation and Work Performance

Independent Variables	Dependent Variable	rho	Interpretation	P-value	Decision	Interpretation
Level of Motivation	Level of Work Performance	.515	Strong	.026	Reject H ₀	Significant
<i>a = 0.05, df = 2</i>						

Table 3 shows the relationship between level of motivation and work performance of teacher. Result reveal that 0.515 spearman rho with strong relationship between the two variables, p-value of 0.026 rejected the null hypotheses and interpreted as there is a significant relationship between the level of motivation and work performance of the teachers. The results imply that the higher the level of motivation, the higher the work performance of the teacher.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The summary of the significant findings of the study was derived from these findings and the corresponding recommendations were made based on the conclusions.

Summary

This study was conducted to determine the level of motivation and work performance of the secondary teachers in eastern samar, Philippines.

The study used a questionnaire to find out the level of motivation and work performance of the teacher. The study utilized frequency count and percentage. The relationship between work performance and level of motivation, the Spearman rho correlation coefficient will be used with 0.05 level of significance in analyzing the data.

Findings

Based on the results, the following findings were formulated:

1. The level of motivation of secondary teachers in eastern samar is high motivating with a 3.51 mean score.
2. The work performance of secondary teachers in eastern samar is very satisfactory with 77.82% or 235 and 22.18% or 67 for outstanding performance of the teacher.
3. There is a significant relationship between the level of motivation and work performance of secondary teachers in eastern samar with 0.515 strong or high and interpreted as a significant relationship.

Conclusion

Based on the results, it was concluded that the level of motivation of the secondary teachers is high motivating and most of them are very satisfactory work performance. Based on the relationship between the variables there was a significant relationship (spearman rho = 0.515; p-value = 0.26) between the level of motivation and work performance of the secondary teachers in the division of eastern samar, Philippines.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are presented:

1. To enhance secondary teachers to learn more in the workplace by providing financial assistance, and harmonious relationships with their co-teacher and administrator.
2. Provide necessary technical assistance for developing teaching and learning development.
3. School administrators should provide technical assistance in terms of teaching strategies to motivate them to learn more in the field of education.
4. Future researchers may conduct similar study to validate the results of the study.

References

- 1) Baluyos, G. R., Rivera, H. L., & Baluyos, E. L. (2019). Teachers' job satisfaction and work performance. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 7(08), 206. <https://www.scirp.org/journal/paperinformation.aspx?paperid=94433>
- 2) Cavendish, W., Connor, D. J., & Perez, D. (2020). Choice, Support, Opportunity: Profiles of Self-Determination in High School Students with Learning Disabilities. *Learning Disabilities: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 25(2), 16-27.
- 3) Fisher, M. H. (2011). Factors Influencing Stress, Burnout, and Retention of Secondary Teachers. *Current Issues in Education*, 14(1).
- 4) Howard, S. K. & Johnson, B. (2018). Resilient teachers: resisting stress and burnout. *Social Psychology of Education*, 7(4), 399-420.
- 5) Jackson, M.J. (2018). Examining the Relationship between School Climate and Teacher Absenteeism, Teacher Job Satisfaction, and Teachers' Intentions to Remain. Proquest Dissertation Publishing
- 6) Keshavarz, M. & Mohammadi, R. (2021). Occupational stress and Organizational performance, Case study: Iran. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 30, 390-394, 10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.10.077.
- 7) Krejcie, R.V., & Morgan, D.W., (1970). Determining Sample Size for Research Activities. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*.
- 8) Louick, R., & Scanlon, D. (2021). Sustained feelings of success and agency: Keys to literacy motivation among adolescents with learning disabilities. *Exceptionality*, 29(1), 1-15.
- 9) Mansfield, C.F., Beltman, S. Weatherby-Fell, N., & Broadley, T. (2016). Classroom ready? Building resilience in teacher education. *Teacher Education: Innovation, intervention and impact*. Singapore
- 10) Mclean, L.; Taylor, M.; Abry, T. & Jimenez, M. (2017). Teachers' Mental Health and Perceptions of School Climate across the Transition from Training to Teaching. *Teaching and Teacher Education* 65, 230-240.
- 11) Oco, R. (2022). Level of job satisfaction of public high school teachers: A survey. *International Journal of Research Publications*, 95. DOI: 10.47119/IJRP100951220222888
- 12) Suson, R. L. (2019). Factors Affecting the Motivational Factors of the 21st Century Educators
- 13) Toste, J. R., Didion, L., Peng, P., Fieldman, M. J., & McClelland, A. M. (2020). A meta-analytic review of the relations between motivation and reading achievement for K–12 students. *Review of Educational Research*, 90(3), 420-456.
- 14) Wehmeyer, M. L., & Shogren, K. A. (2020). Self-Determination and Autonomous Motivation: Implications for Students with Intellectual, Developmental, and Specific Learning Disabilities. In *Handbook of educational psychology and students with special needs* (pp. 262-291). Routledge.